

Functional Outcomes of Arthroscopic Suture Fixation for Tibial Eminence Fracture of ACLSourabh Cholkar^{1*}, Abhishek Pathak², Santosh Mishra³, Rahul Rohilla¹¹MS Orthopaedics, PG Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College & Associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India²MS Orthopaedics, Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College & Associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India³MS Orthopaedics, Assistant professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College & Associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Although relatively rare, anterior tibial spine fractures are becoming more common due to increased participation in athletic activities and motor vehicle accidents. These fractures often require operative intervention for proper knee stability and functionality. Arthroscopic suture fixation is a minimally invasive technique that offers several benefits, including anatomic reduction and early mobilization.**Aim and Objective:** To evaluate the functional outcomes of arthroscopic suture fixation for tibial eminence fractures of the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) using the pull-through suture technique.**Materials and Methods:** This prospective study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, and Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, from December 2020 to September 2022. Twenty patients aged 8 to 60 years with anterior tibial spine avulsion fractures classified as Meyers and McKeever Type II and III were included. Preoperative evaluations included knee instability tests, X-rays, MRIs, and routine laboratory investigations. Arthroscopic-assisted pull-through suture ligation was performed, followed by a structured postoperative care and rehabilitation protocol. Patients were followed up at 1, 3, 6, and 9 months. Functional outcomes were assessed using the Lysholm Tegner score.**Results:** The mean age of the patients was 25.4 years (SD \pm 9.88), with a male predominance (90%). The right side was affected in 60% of cases. Students were the most commonly affected group (35%). The primary mode of injury was sports-related (50%). Preoperative Lysholm Tegner scores were uniformly below 65, indicating poor knee function. Postoperatively, 70% of patients achieved excellent scores (>90), and 25% achieved good scores (84-90). The mean preoperative score improved significantly from 51.05 (SD \pm 8.53) to 92.10 (SD \pm 4.59) at the 9-month follow-up ($p < 0.0001$). Complications were minimal, with only two cases of knee stiffness and one minor extension lag.**Conclusion:** The arthroscopic pull-through suture technique for tibial eminence fractures of the ACL is highly effective, resulting in significant improvements in knee function and stability with minimal complications. This technique offers the advantages of anatomic reduction, secure fixation, and early mobilization, making it a preferred method for managing these fractures. Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to validate these findings.**Keywords:** ACL, Tibial Spine Fractures, Arthroscopic Suture Fixation, Knee Stability, Functional Outcomes, Minimally Invasive Surgery.

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Introduction

Anterior tibial spine fractures, though relatively rare, have an incidence of approximately 3 per 100,000 per year. [1] These fractures are more frequently observed in children and adolescents, particularly those aged 8 to 14 years, due to the relative weakness of the incompletely ossified tibial eminence compared to the native anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) fibers. [2, 3] The avulsion of the ACL represents 2% to 5% of knee injuries. [4] However, the increasing prevalence of athletic

activities among children and high-energy motor vehicle accidents among adults have contributed to a rise in the incidence of these fractures in both demographics. [5]

The primary mechanisms of injury include motor vehicle accidents and contact sports, such as football, cricket, and hockey. [6] The injury typically results from forceful hyperextension of the knee with a rotational component, leading to

extreme tensile forces on the ACL, which causes an avulsion of the tibial eminence rather than an intrasubstance rupture of the ligament. [7-9] Meyers and McKeever classified avulsion fractures into three types: Type I (undisplaced), Type II (partially displaced with an intact posterior hinge), and Type III (completely displaced). [10] Later, Zaricznyj introduced a fourth category, Type IV, to describe comminuted avulsed fragments. [11]

Treating displaced (Type II or Type III/IV) fractures is often operative to ensure proper knee stability and functionality. Arthroscopic reduction and fixation have gained popularity due to their minimally invasive nature, limited skin incision, and reduced soft-tissue injury. [6-7] Various fixation devices, including screws, staples, tension wiring, K wires, sutures, and anchor sutures, have been utilized during arthroscopy. Among these, arthroscopic suture fixation has shown promise, particularly in its ability to provide anatomic reduction and reliable fixation, restore ACL length and integrity, and avoid needing a second surgery to remove hardware. [1, 7-9]

This study aims to evaluate the functional outcomes of arthroscopic suture fixation for tibial eminence fractures of the ACL. We hypothesize that this minimally invasive technique can effectively restore knee stability and range of motion, offering a reliable alternative to traditional fixation methods. The study focuses on the pull-through suture technique, assessing its efficacy in achieving satisfactory clinical results in patients with ACL avulsion fractures.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, and Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, from December 2020 to September 2022. Twenty patients presenting with an avulsion fracture of the tibial eminence of the ACL were included in the study. The study aimed to evaluate the functional outcomes of arthroscopic suture fixation using the pull-through suture ligation technique.

Patients included in this study were those who provided informed consent and were willing to follow up. They were aged between 8 and 60 years and had anterior tibial spine avulsion fractures classified as Meyers and McKeever Type II and III. Additionally, all patients were fit for anesthesia and surgery. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients who refused to consent to surgery or were unwilling to undergo postoperative rehabilitation. Patients with surgical contraindications for medical, anesthetic, or surgical reasons were also excluded. Furthermore, individuals with anterior tibial spine avulsion fractures classified as Meyers and McKeever Type I and IV, those with associated bony injuries in the ipsilateral leg, and patients with

intraligamentous ACL damage or injuries to the MCL, LCL, medial menisci, or lateral menisci in the ipsilateral limb were not included in the study.

Preoperative Evaluation

Eligible patients who provided consent were included in the study. Detailed history and examination findings were recorded prospectively using a case record form. Knee instability was examined using the Lachman test, anterior drawer test, pivot shift test, and varus-valgus stress test. Preoperative X-rays of the knee joint were taken to classify the injury according to Meyers and McKeever's classification. MRI of the knee joint was also performed preoperatively. Routine laboratory investigations included CBC, LFT, RFT, RBS, S. electrolytes, BT, CT, viral markers, urine routine and microscopic examination. Lysholm Tegner's scores were noted preoperatively. Written and oral consent was obtained from the patients, and the procedure, risks, and proposed benefits were clearly explained. Follow-up of the patients was conducted at 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 9 months postoperatively. All patients underwent primary arthroscopic-assisted pull-through suture ligation surgery.

Surgical Technique

Instruments and Implants: Arthroscopic portal cannulas with obturators, 30-degree arthroscope, fiber-optic light, irrigation system, arthroscopic burr and shaver system, arthroscopic grasper, arthroscopic scissors, guide wires and reamers, endobutton, and digital radiography were utilized for the procedure.

Patient Positioning: Intravenous antibiotics (commonly ceftriaxone 1g IV) were administered one hour before the tourniquet inflation. All surgeries were performed under spinal anesthesia. Patients were positioned supine on the operating table with their legs extended and their feet at the end of the table. The thigh was padded with a cotton bandage, and the tourniquet cuff was applied. A circular adhesive drape was placed distal to the tourniquet cuff to prevent soaking the cotton bandage with arthroscopy fluid. A lateral post was attached to the operating table to position the leg at 90° flexion.

The surgical procedure began with creating a standard anterolateral portal for the arthroscope. Diagnostic arthroscopy was then performed to assess the tibial spine fracture and any associated injuries. An anteromedial portal was created for instrumentation. The fracture site was cleared of soft tissue using an arthroscopic shaver. The avulsed fragment was then reduced and fixed using a pull-through suture technique. Sutures were passed through the ACL substance and tied over an endobutton on the medial and lateral tibial tunnels. The reduction was confirmed arthroscopically, and

the stability of the fixation was checked. Finally, the portals were closed, and a sterile dressing was applied.

Postoperative Care and Rehabilitation: Postoperatively, patients were advised to use crutches for partial weight bearing for six weeks, followed by a gradual increase in weight bearing as tolerated. Range-of-motion exercises were initiated immediately, focusing on achieving full extension. Strengthening exercises for the quadriceps and hamstrings were progressively introduced. Regular follow-ups were conducted to monitor the progress, with clinical and radiological assessments performed each visit.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected prospectively, including patient demographics, mechanism of injury, type of fracture, preoperative and postoperative Lysholm Tegner scores, and complications. Statistical analysis was performed using appropriate methods to evaluate the outcomes of the surgical technique.

Results

Demographic Data: A total of 20 patients were included in this prospective observational study. The age distribution of the patients is shown in Table 1. The majority of the patients, 40%, were in the 20-30-year age group, followed by 35% in the 8-20-year age group, 15% in the 30-40-year age group, and 10% above 40 years. The mean age was 25.4 years (SD± 9.88), with the youngest patient being ten years old and the oldest 45 years old. Out of the 20 patients, 18 were male (90%), and two were female (10%), indicating a male predominance in the occurrence of tibial eminence fractures. In this study, the right side was more commonly affected, with 12 patients (60%) having right-sided fractures and 8 patients (40%) having left-sided fractures. The occupation distribution of the patients revealed that students were the most commonly affected group, accounting for 35% of the cases, followed by workers (30%), office staff (20%), and others (15%). The predominant mode of injury was sports-related, accounting for 50% of the cases, followed by road traffic accidents (30%), falls (15%), and other causes (5%).

Table 1: Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic		Number of Patients	Percentage
Age; years	8-20	7	35%
	20-30	8	40%
	30-40	3	15%
	>40	2	10%
Gender	Male	18	90%
	Female	2	10%
Side affected	Right Side	12	60%
	Left Side	8	40%
Occupation	Students	7	35%
	Workers	6	30%
	Office Staff	4	20%
	Others	3	15%
Mode of injury	Sports	10	50%
	Road Traffic Accidents	6	30%
	Fall	3	15%
	Other	1	5%

Injury Operation Interval: The interval between injury and operation was analyzed. 60% of the patients were operated on within 5-10 days of injury, 30% were operated on after more than ten days, and 10% were operated on within 5 days of injury.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients According to Injury Operation Interval

Injury Operation Interval (Days)	Number of Patients	Percentage
<5	2	10%
5-10	12	60%
>10	6	30%

Fracture Classification: According to the Meyers and McKeever classification, 65% of the patients had Type 3 fractures, while 35% had Type 2 fractures.

Table 3: Distribution of Patients According to Meyers and McKeever Classification

Meyers and McKeever Type	Number of Patients	Percentage
Type 2	7	35%
Type 3	13	65%

Preoperative and Postoperative Lysholm Tegner Scores: The preoperative Lysholm Tegner scores were uniformly below 65 for all patients, indicating poor knee function before surgery. Postoperatively, 70% of the patients achieved excellent scores (>90), 25% achieved good scores (84-90), 5% had

fair scores (65-83), and none had poor scores (<65). The mean preoperative score was 51.05 (SD± 8.53), which significantly improved to 92.10 (SD± 4.59) at the 9-month follow-up (p-value=0.0001).

Table 4: Distribution of Patients According to Pre-op Lysholm Tegner Score

Lysholm Tegner Score	Number of Patients	Percentage
>90	0	0%
84-90	0	0%
65-83	0	0%
<65	20	100%

Table 5: Distribution of Patients According to Post-op Lysholm Tegner Score

Lysholm Tegner Score	Number of Patients	Percentage
>90	14	70%
84-90	5	25%
65-83	1	5%
<65	0	0%

Complications

The study reported minimal complications. No patients experienced postoperative infections, significant knee stiffness, or implant-related issues. One patient had a minor extension lag of 5 degrees, which did not affect overall function.

Discussion

Due to the increased frequency of road traffic accidents, sports activities, and high-demand work, the occurrence of anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries has risen. ACL avulsion fractures are more common than posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) avulsions. [2-4] Traditional open fixation methods often result in knee stiffness due to extensive dissection and prolonged immobilization. Arthroscopic techniques, particularly suture fixation, offer advantages such as anatomic reduction, secure fixation, and early range of motion, which help prevent stiffness and restore full extension.

In this study, 20 patients with tibial eminence fractures were treated using the arthroscopic pull-through suture technique. The average age of the patients was 25.4 years, with the majority in the 20-30 year age group (40%), followed by the 8-20 year age group (35%). This age distribution aligns with previous studies, including those by Koukoulas et al., [12], who reported a mean patient age of 29.9 years, and Ballal et al., [13], with a mean age of 27.13. Similar age distributions were found in studies by Kumar Kishore et al. [14] (30.3 years) and Sapre et al. [15] (29.2 years).

The male predominance (90% male, 10% female) observed in this study is consistent with other research, including Pandey et al. (88.5% males) [16], Das BK (80% males), [17] and Kumar Kishore et al. [14] (66.6% males). This high proportion can be

explained by the tendency of male patients to participate in intense outdoor and high-risk activities for occupational and recreational purposes. Males are more likely to be involved in road traffic accidents and combat sports, making them prone to sports-related injuries.

In this study, the right side was more commonly involved in avulsion fractures of the anterior tibial spine (60% right side, 40% left side), similar to findings by Kumar Mohit et al., where 6 out of 10 patients had right-side injuries. Saud F. et al. [18] also concluded that most ACL injuries occur in the dominant leg.

Students were the most commonly affected group in this study (35%), followed by workers (30%), office staff (20%), and others (15%). The predominance of students can be attributed to their participation in sports and other physical activities.

The primary mode of injury in this study was sports-related (50%), followed by road traffic accidents (30%) and falls (15%). This distribution is consistent with studies by Ballal M M et al. (73.3% RTA, 20% sports, 6.7% falls) and Kumar Kishore et al. [14] (62.5% RTA, 26.3% sports, 3.17% falls). Das BK [17] reported 60% RTA and 30% sports injuries.

According to the Meyers and McKeever classification, 65% of patients had Type 3 fractures, and 35% had Type 2 fractures. The Lysholm Tegner scores showed significant improvement postoperatively, with mean scores increasing from 51.05 preoperatively to 92.10 at the nine-month follow-up. Similar improvements were observed in studies by Russu et al., [19], who reported a significant increase in Lysholm scores from 53.7 to 87.7, and Chawda et al., [20], with a final follow-up score of 86.8.

Complications were minimal, with two patients experiencing knee stiffness and one having a minor extension lag of 5 degrees, which did not significantly affect overall function. No cases of postoperative infection or significant residual laxity were reported. Kocher et al. [21] concluded that arthroscopic fixation of type III tibial spine fractures resulted in persistent laxity but excellent functional outcomes. Osti et al. [22] reported laxity in 30% of cases but no extension deficit.

Overall, the arthroscopic pull-through suture technique provides excellent functional outcomes with minimal complications, supporting its use as a preferred method for managing tibial spine avulsion fractures. Future studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are warranted to validate these findings further.

Conclusion

The arthroscopic pull-through suture technique for tibial eminence fractures of the ACL has proven to be highly effective, resulting in significant improvements in knee function and stability, as evidenced by the substantial increase in postoperative Lysholm Tegner scores. The procedure is associated with minimal complications, such as minor knee stiffness and extension lag, which did not adversely affect overall function. The technique offers the advantages of anatomic reduction, secure fixation, and early mobilization, making it a preferred method for managing these fractures. This study supports using the arthroscopic pull-through suture technique as a reliable and effective treatment option for ACL avulsion fractures, with excellent functional outcomes and a low complication rate. Future studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to validate these findings further and optimize treatment protocols.

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